

Efforts to Overcome a Plateau in Learning for Elementary School Students

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Abstract:- Plateau in learning is a condition in which students undergo a decrease in learning effectivity, learning motivation, as well as physical and emotional exhaustion. Ways to tackle boredom in learning can be carried out through different learning methods, student approaches, and evaluations. In addition, it can be conducted by creating a delighted learning state, bringing out motivation and stimulus, and changing students' learning schedules. This study is a systematic review of the literature to identify, review, and analyze the research results according to relevant findings, which are systematically selected from the literature and further followed by structured steps. The findings show that boredom in learning occurs to the entire students, while variation and teacher's creativity in learning help to overcome a plateau in learning and suppress boredom while the learning process.

Keywords:- A Plateau in Learning, Overcoming Plateau in Learning, Elementary School

I. INTRODUCTION

No education is without a natural learning process since learning is the most crucial element in all efforts to organize the type and level of education. The success or failure of educational goals highly depend on learning and educational process, which students and educators underwent at school and in their families [1]. Moreover, every individual must study to achieve the educational goals. Individuals should know what to do to reach learning effectiveness [2]. Whilst it is teacher's job to provide learning environment, otherwise, student's job is to study. These two activities are called educational interaction. A conducive environment is a place where students encourage to study every time [3].

The learning process, according to students, is to develop creative thinking and enlarge their knowledge to master subject materials. The number of demands and student's activity often burden students, and the long-term stress cause boredom in learning [4]. Feeling of forgetfulness and boredom in learning on students toward the learning process is the familiar thing. Although forgetfulness/saturation has become human nature, efforts are needed to reduce it. Students who have poor memory and feel bored during learning remain a dilemma that cannot be separated from educators. In addition, boredom in learning becomes an obstacle in the process of delivering knowledge to students [1].

Students who are in boredom condition feel stuck on their knowledge and skills, which they get through learning. The lack of learning progress does not last long, but it is only for certain times. However, students gradually feel exhausted to learn, especially in the certain stages from their instructional activity. Additionally, from those who feel bored while learning process, they tend to forget and experience another negative event unless [5].

Students, who get bored during learning, will have difficulty processing new information and experience, as a result, the system may not function properly when it gets bored and fed up with the situation. As a result, student learning outcomes are inappropriate for the planned and educational goals [6].

An aspect of tiresome learning is the excessive learning demand. In addition, a school's educational saturation is also associated with boredom. Exhausted learning is also a factor to be less optimally impacted by the learning process. Getting bored during learning is a common situation occurred in students. When bored, they reluctantly accept the materials teachers deliver during the learning process [7].

The atmosphere that tends to be monotonous in learning activities can also lead to apathy, that is caused to lose self-confidence on students and the understanding of materials delivered by teachers. Boredom in learning can cause uncontrolled emotion and frustration [8].

The high demands at school and education resulted in boredom during learning. Also, during the learning process in class, boredom is created by psychological pressure and other learning. This affects students who reluctantly attend classes as well as are less motivated to learn, emotionally bored, and inactive. Boredom can also affect a student's academic performance. Students who experience boredom while studying suffer from poor performance despite routine learning activities (Satrio et al., 2020).

Students experiencing a period of learning stagnation may not be able to process new information and experiences as expected because students who feel bored cannot do their job. Humanly, boredom can happen to anyone, including students, studying. In other words, boredom is not about age or condition. Because of this, if students get bored, they need to deal quickly and appropriately and not let it go. Similarly, what happens to students, we often find some students with learning disabilities (Satrio et al., 2020).

II. METHOD

A systematic literature review is a method used in this study. This research identifies, reviews, and analyzes the results of the research, withdraws an assessment, interprets, and concludes according to the relevance findings that is systematically selected based on themes from literature. Furthermore, it refers to what has decided by following the structured steps [9]. Sources of references are searched by browsing articles in Indonesian and English. The search is related to a plateau in the learning process of elementary school students, and further analysis is implemented.

Researchers look for references on Google Scholar with the keywords plateau in learning and student learning exhaustion in elementary schools. As a result, researchers found 39 articles. Then, articles from national and international journals were observed, reviewed, and analyzed. The following lists are the references that the researcher has found:

Table 1. Lists of the Research References

Year of Publication	International Journal	National Journal
2022		4
2021		7
2020	1	4
2019		2
2018		3
2017		
2016		2
Total	1	22

Table 2. Authors classified by subject

	Authors
Learning plateau	[3], [7], [8], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17]
Overcoming the Learning Plateau in the Learning of Elementary School	[1], [2], [4], [5], [6], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23],

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Learning Plateau

In learning activities, people often experience learning saturation, which is “a plateau in learning” in psychological science. This situation or condition shows the ineffectiveness of learning outcomes, even though the learning process is carried out at a certain time. The good system cannot absorb information due to stagnation in the brain system [10].

Boredom in learning is defined as low learning result, deliberated performance in the learning activity, ignorance, negative attitude, inappropriate behavior like pretending and lying, and other negative customs such as skipping school, arriving late, not doing homework, not wanting to take notes, being confused during learning activity, etc [18].

A plateau in learning is a period when several trials in the learning sequence do not change the slope of the learning curve, which indicates that the learning effort has stopped for a while. This stabilization period can occur due to fatigue, loss of motivation, or consolidation of skill levels before reaching a higher level [11].

Learning exhaustion can mainly be seen through emotional states. It is characterized by fatigue (self-control and anxiety), loss of motivation (loss of enthusiasm), loss of ambition, frustration, resignation, etc.), and cognitive fatigue (inability to concentrate, inability to perform complex tasks, loneliness, and reduced stamina in the face of perceived frustration) [12].

The main cause of boredom in learning is that students felt exhausted. An exhaustion cause students bored with the existing situation. A plenty of tasks make them depressed, feel emotionally bored that leads to poor quality instruction. Student’s mentally and physically exhausted make them unwilling to study, decrease motivation, and reduce their self-confidence in learning [19].

The literal meaning of the word “exhausted” is convinced or tremendously complete, in addition, being exhausted also means boring. If a student in the educational process encounters an event that makes them feel tired, it can be interpreted that the student feels like a waste of time. Learning exhaustion is time spent while studying but does not get some results [20]. Burnout is when individuals are physically, mentally, and emotionally exhausted, unsupported, or work profoundly long [21].

Study boredom is the mental state of someone when experiencing extreme boredom and laziness, resulting in a feeling of laziness, lack of enthusiasm, or lack of enthusiasm in learning activities [11]. Learning exhaustion is a situation when students are in a state of learning, but at that time, they are not able to process the information in their brains, as a result, what they have done is meaningless [6].

Boredom occurs during studying as a negative work-related experience with aspects of fatigue and abandonment of work. Fatigue is defined as the result of persistence and frequent physical activity and leads to cognitive aspects and emotional impairment from stress persistence in the learning process [13].

A plateau's three aspects in learning are emotional fatigue, depersonalization, and personal achievement. The workload is too high, which further causes emotional malaise. Depersonalization is a condition in which a person is withdrawn due to cynical feelings towards others and tries to move away from them for fear of being disappointed in the social environment. Personal achievement is the stage at which one becomes pessimistic about one's abilities [13].

Four factors cause learning fatigue in children, as follows:

1. Because of the child's anxiety about the negative effects of fatigue itself.
2. Because children's anxiety about standards or benchmarks of success in certain fields of study is considered too high, especially when they get bored with the former studies.
3. Because children are in a situation of intense competition and intense mental work.
4. Because children learn the concept of optimal learning outcomes when they only evaluate learning according to the orientation they have made themselves [22].

There are four demands from school that are identified able to affect student's boredom in learning:

1. *Physical demands* are understood as pressure that students experience due to the physical school environment.
2. *Task demands* are school activities that are very helpful for the development and advancement of students; besides, it frequently causes depression and anxiety.
3. *Role demands* are usually related to behavioral expectations communicated by schools, parents, and communities. Behavioral expectations can be sources of boredom for students, especially when they cannot fulfill their role expectations.
4. *An academic stressor* for interpersonal demands can be differentiated to two kinds that cause boredom in school:
 - a. The social-personal stressor is stress caused by students and their social environment.
 - b. An academic stressor is a student's boredom with teaching-learning activities [18].

Meanwhile, Armand T. Fabella, as followed by Rismalia Sari [11], states that personal signs of learning saturation can be divided into two: physical, psychological, and behavioral. From a physical point of view, students experiencing learning saturation symptoms are physical fatigue, feeling weak, frequent headaches, indigestion, difficulty sleeping, and shortness of breath. Meanwhile, in terms of psychology and behavior, namely, work harder. Still, performance decreases, feel bored and confused, have low morale, feel uncomfortable, feel useless and find it difficult to make decisions [11].

This can cause students to become bored with their studies because they react negatively to stress. Distress and eustress are two opposite directions. Stress can produce more positive outcomes depending on how students respond to the

stimulus. Feeling bored in learning gradually increase if students show type of distress otherwise, boredom will decrease if students show eustress [14].

B. *Overcoming a Plateau in Learning of Elementary School*

The efforts that need to be made to overcome the boredom of learning while studying are as follows:

1. Applying Different Learning Methods

Teachers must try to use the right method in educating students, it can be adjusting the psychological condition of students; besides, they must pay attention to the learning methods used and the delivery of material that students easily accept.

2. Approaching Students

Engaging students to overcome student boredom. The emotional approach is very important and must be done, and it needs to be faced and given special attention regularly. Teachers should create a learning atmosphere that is enjoyable and not tense; as a result, students are interested in participating in the learning process.

3. Conducting evaluations

Teachers are expected to be able to design supportive teaching and learning interactions to serve as indicators of educational success. In addition, the learning process requires teachers to follow up on the learning outcomes achieved by students through evaluation. The information obtained is used as a starting point for improvement and further refinement of the learning process [23].

Other ways can help overcome boredom while studying. Some suggestions that teachers can look for and use to tackle boredom while studying are as follows:

1. Always Discovering the New Things.

Smart teachers need to have different skills in the teaching process. These skills are intended not only for learning purposes but also for stimulating students' enthusiasm for learning. Teachers who can communicate their presence in the classroom are always loved by their students. However, under the guidance of an unskilled teacher, students are prone to burnout and throw tantrums in class.

2. Doing Continuous Learning

It is needed to update our knowledge and brain by learning new things. Learn new things that happen on the job or by taking courses and training. Learning increases confidence and the ability to handle more difficult tasks.

3. Being Creative and Proactive

Finding fresh ideas enhances creative and active learning or develops your ideas for clear and useful learning goals. Then, if you succeed in achieving it, you can reward yourself with a gift.

4. Managing a Schedule

It is easy to get bored with just "living" to work. Before leaving for work, somebody requires to do fun activities [10].

In addition, the following are tips that can be carried out to tackle boredom:

1. Changing or rescheduling study time to make students study harder
2. Creating new motivations and stimulating on which students to feel motivated and encouraged to study harder rather than previously conducted.
3. Changing or organizing a re-learning environment for students [1].

Students who feel exhausted due to boredom do not realize their abilities and do not engage in self-regulated learning. Applying self-regulated learning, which tends to affect positivity toward learning success, is by managing their self-study time, realizing their learning style suitable to their ability, and avoiding boredom due to monotonous learning. Self-regulated learning is an individual effort to address self-activity, engage metacognitive skills, enhance motivation, and do positive behavior. Students who can monitor, regulate, control, and learning motivation are more likely to achieve maximum learning outcomes [15].

Students should have learning motivation to overcome the boredom in learning. Motivation can raise students' enthusiasm for learning. Without motivation, students will not be enthusiastic in learning. Learning motivation can affect student learning outcomes, if student motivation is lacking, it will not achieve optimal learning outcomes [16].

The teacher's role as educator is very important for the selection and development of innovative and meaningful strategies to encourage student learning motivation. Furthermore, they can reach optimal learning goals. An innovative learning is not only carried out with collaborative learning model, but it is also supported by media to deepen students' understanding and make their interest to be more meaningful [17].

As research by Ayunda Roham [6], he developed the model of mind-mapping to tackle boredom in learning. This method eases students to understand materials they learnt and overcome the boredom. A mind-mapping gives them a liberty to express creativity and imagination without burdening the studied materials [6].

IV. CONCLUSION

A plateau in learning can occurs to the entire students. Plateau in learning is a condition in which students undergo a decrease in learning effectivity, learning motivation, and physical and emotional exhaustion. Signs of learning boredom are physical fatigue, feeling weak, frequent headaches, indigestion, sleeping difficulty, and dyspnea (shortness of breath). Ways to tackle boredom in learning can be carried out through different learning methods, student approaches, and evaluations. In addition, it can be conducted by creating a delighted learning state, bringing out motivation and stimulus, and changing students' learning schedules.

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